

USING EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR EFFECTIVE DELIVERY OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract.

In this article the information is given about the technologies based on education in distance learning. The article also clarifies how to use these technologies during e-learning and structures of utilizing a new platform called “Nearpod”.

Аннотация.

В данной статье дается информация о технологиях, основанных на дистанционном обучении. В статье также разъясняется, как использовать эти технологии во время электронного обучения, и структуры использования новой платформы под названием «Nearpod».

Kalit sòzlar: masofaviy ta'lim, ta'lim texnologiyalari, blended learning, vebinar texnologiyalar, "Nearpod " platformasi.

Key words: distance learning, learning technologies, blended learning, webinar technologies, platform "Nearpod".

Ключевые слова: дистанционное обучение, технологии обучения, смешанное обучение, вебинарные технологии, платформа Nearpod.

Introduction

Educational technology is one of the broad fields. Educational technology is considered as a science that studies or designs the fundamentals of learning, teaching and social and practical application and a complex of various research interests.

Educational technology - (eng. "an educational technology") the organization of the educational process at the level of high skill and art.

Distance education - delivery of the main volume of the studied material to students, interactive interaction of students and teachers during the teaching process, allowing students to work independently on the independent mastering of the studied material and study a set of information technologies that provide assessment of the knowledge and skills they have acquired in the process.

Literature review

We know that in recent decades, the development of distance education has become the focus of the world community as a means of continuous education. In particular, in March 1990, the European Commission adopted the working document "Distance education and vocational training". This document states that high-quality educational technologies can be developed at the center and then distributed locally. In 1994, the European Commission launched the "Leonardo da Vinci" program in order to create favorable conditions for distance education. This program is a system derived from the experiences of "artists, scientists, poets and writers who created new forms of continuous education and training throughout their lives." The "Socrates" program helped to realize the goal of "bringing home education to the European scale."

Another advantage of distance education is that the student can study at his own convenience and even without leaving work. It is because of these advantages that this method is widely used in the world today. Especially during the coronavirus pandemic, which has become a global problem and worries everyone, the entire world education system has switched to distance education.

In order to clarify the distance education and its forms, Distance education technologies are a set of forms, methods and tools aimed at ensuring the implementation of education based on the specified content[1].

Distance learning technologies include the following forms:

- Blended learning
- Webinar technologies

Blended learning is a form of learning based on online learning materials and group learning under the guidance of a teacher.

Blended learning includes the following European education models:

1. Distance learning
2. Audience education (face to face learning)
3. Internet education (online learning)
4. Lifelong learning

Blended learning in HEIs is based on the following:

1. Online lectures
2. Online practical training
3. Project and group work discussed on the Internet
4. Laboratory classes organized online
5. Self-administered online test
6. Online consultation

Webinar technologies (eng. "webinar" - web-based seminar) is a type of seminar organized on the basis of mutual unity of web technologies and traditional education.

By mastering these technologies, pedagogues - teachers get the opportunity to organize interactive training sessions. Students can use online education efficiently while saving their time and participate in practical training and seminars that meet world standards.[2]

One of the most popular and effective educational technologies for distance learning with students today is Nearpod.

Research Methodology

Nearpod is an online platform that teachers can use in the classroom to help students learn. This platform allows the teacher to ask open-ended questions for students that they can write answers to and to represent the answers in pictures. In it, students can describe their work in writing or, if necessary, show it with a drawing. Nearpod allows all students to join a single class and each student has their own space where the teacher can give them feedback on their answers. Also, through the Nearpod online board, students can see the answers given by their peers, because all the answers are displayed on the online board. If we talk about the entertainment side of the platform, the game "Time to Climb" is very important. There, the student chooses an animal, and for each correct answer to the question, they climb higher and higher up the mountain.

Overall, the Nearpod platform has been one of the most useful and effective online platforms for teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In order to make it easier to use this platform, we would like to highlight some of the features of Nearpod and how to create exercises on it.

How to co-teach with Nearpod?

With Nearpod co-teaching, you and your partner can control the pace of the lesson and provide simultaneous insights into student responses.

Here's how to add a co-teacher to the Nearpod platform:

1. Start your Nearpod lesson in live participation mode as usual.
2. When the code appears, you can add a co-teacher link. Enable this option and copy the link.

3. Share the link with your colleague. Invite them to join the class. After your

colleague enters his name and clicks the "Join lesson" button, he will join the lesson as a co-teacher.

What can and cannot be done by a teacher conducting a joint lesson? You can get an answer to this question through the application given below.

Teacher Colleague

Lesson Management:

Go to presentation	yes	no
Start at the specified time.	yes	yes
With the students' answers to share	yes.	yes

Confirmation of messages in partnership	yes	yes
Completion of the lesson	yes	no
Control the playback mode of the video.	yes	yes
Switch to student view	yes	yes
View student answers	yes	yes

Excluding students from classes is not allowed

Another good thing about the Nearpod platform is that you can easily create interactive videos. Here's a step-by-step guide on how to create a video on Qui:

Video instruction is a great way to teach students new information. With Nearpod, you can add any questions directly to the video and make the video interactive.

Start from the My Library page, then select Create Video on the left.

In Nearpod, the teacher can create a video himself, search YouTube or use videos from the platform's library.

After selecting the video, select the place where you want to add a question during the video and click the "Add Activity" button.

Save your question.

Once you're done, you can add a title to your video by clicking the pencil in the blue bar above your video, then save your video by clicking the Save button at the bottom right.

Culture, it turns out, is the way that every brain makes sense of the world," writes Zaretta Hammond in *Culturally Responsive Teaching & the Brain*.^[3] We process new information by relating to our own experiences and interests. By including diverse perspectives, cultures, and narratives in the instruction, teachers help ensure all students have access to the connections needed to process information effectively and meaningfully. In this circumstance, Nearpod's multimedia is the best option to process the information, such as virtual reality, video, and web content, to integrate culturally relevant content into the classroom instruction.

In *Culturally Responsive Teaching & the Brain*^[3], Hammond describes three levels of culture: surface culture, shallow culture, and deep culture. Culture's visible aspects, such as food, art, and holidays, are referred to as surface culture. Teachers could take their pupils on a virtual reality journey to different parts of the world so they can see surface culture firsthand. However, it's equally crucial to talk about the facets of culture that a VR image cannot capture. Examining is demanded whether the media has shallow culture, which consists of unwritten laws similar to forms of non-verbal communication. Is deep culture—the presumptions that govern our worldview and its components, including ethics and spirituality—present in the media? It should be considered to employ primary source media, such as video interviews and podcasts, as well as including SEL topics, such as perspective-taking and valuing diversity, to integrate deeper levels of culture. To get started, it is appropriate to look at our SEL & Our Stories: Race & Ethnicity of the platform Nearpod.

Conclusion and Discussion.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that educational technologies are diverse. Using them during the lesson is important not only in increasing the student's learning efficiency, but also in making the lesson interactive. The use of such technologies in distance education is a modern demand.

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